

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF MONITORING THE ACQUISITION OF KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS AND ABILITIES BY STUDENTS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN UNIVERSITIES

Kholbaeva Dilorom Dusiyarovna¹, Tasheva Dilorom Salimovna²

^{1,2} Researcher of Samarkand State University veterinary medicine of
livestock and biotechnologies, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7192304>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st October 2022

Accepted: 05th October 2022

Online: 13th October 2022

KEY WORDS

learning process, content, methods, means, forms, skill, abilities, assessment pedagogy, conscientious work, completeness, strength, depth, efficiency, flexibility.

ABSTRACT

An important condition for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process is the systematic receipt by the teacher of objective information about the progress of educational and cognitive activity of students. The teacher receives this information in the process of monitoring the educational and cognitive activity of students. This article studies modern psychological and pedagogical literature to characterize various methods, types and forms of control and assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities in Russian language lessons in university. Moreover, it reveals the features of various methods, types and forms of organization of control and assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities of students.

Control means identifying, establishing and evaluating students' knowledge. Determining the volume, level and quality of assimilation of educational material, identifying academic success, gaps in knowledge, skills and abilities of individual students and the entire class to make the necessary adjustments to the learning process, to improve its content, methods, means and forms of organization.

The main task of control is to identify the level of correctness, volume, depth and validity of the knowledge acquired by students, obtaining information about the nature of cognitive activity, about the level of independence and activity of students in the educational process, determining the

effectiveness of methods, forms and methods of their teaching.

Performing the function of managing the educational and cognitive activity of students, control is not always accompanied by grading. It can act as a way to prepare students for the perception of new material, to identify students' readiness to master knowledge, skills and abilities, to generalize and systematize them. Control has an important educational and developmental value.

The pedagogical functions of control consist in identifying shortcomings in the work of students, establishing their nature and causes in order to eliminate these shortcomings. It is important for the teacher to have information both about the

assimilation of knowledge by students, and about how they were obtained.

Control also plays an important educational role in the learning process. It helps to increase the responsibility for the work performed not only by the student, but also by the teacher. Teaching students to systematic work and accuracy in the performance of educational tasks.

In general, testing knowledge is a form of consolidation, clarification. Comprehension and systematization of students' knowledge. Listening to the answering comrade, the students at the same time, as it were, repeat again what they themselves learned the day before. And the better the check is organized, the more conditions for such consolidation.

Testing knowledge is a form of pedagogical control over the educational activities of students. If we take into account that the main educational task of the teacher is to ensure that the entire program volume of knowledge is mastered by the students, it becomes clear that one cannot do without a special knowledge test. Moreover, it must be organized in such a way that real knowledge is revealed as deeply and fully as possible.

Checking is an incentive for regular classes, for conscientious work of students. In this respect, the element of probability and surprise present in most cases of verification is undoubtedly useful.

Testing students' knowledge is the most important objective form of teacher's self-control. A teacher's self-assessment will be truly objective if the knowledge test is organized in such a way that ensures the most complete identification of this knowledge.

Therefore, control is an important and necessary component of learning and

involves the teacher's systematic observation of the progress of learning at all stages of the educational process.

Under the assessment of student progress is meant a system of certain indicators that reflect the objective knowledge and skills of the student.

In the Pedagogical Encyclopedia, assessment is considered as determining the degree of assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities by students in accordance with the requirements imposed on them by university programs.

The assessment takes into account the volume, level and quality of students' mastery of knowledge, skills and abilities. The volume of knowledge in a particular subject is a list of leading concepts, laws, ideas of theories that underlie this science and are interpreted in university curricula.

Mastering the volume of leading theoretical knowledge precedes the formation of certain purposeful actions in the student: either the reproduction of what has been learned or its application in an image, in similar conditions; roofing felts the use of what has been learned to solve non-standard complex mental problems. All this sets one or another level of knowledge acquisition, i.e. the nature of the application of acquired knowledge, providing one or another degree of mental effort (the level of mental activity). Different levels of knowledge assimilation are determined by its quality, which means certain characters, characteristics of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities (for example, completeness, strength, depth, efficiency, flexibility, efficiency, etc.) in addition; the assessment reflects not only the volume, level and quality of knowledge assimilation. Its functions are complex and varied.

The social function is manifested in the requirements imposed by society on the level of preparation of a student. The education in this case is used as a broad concept that includes the age level of development, education and awareness of the student, the formation of his cognitive, emotional and volitional spheres of personality.

In the course of control, the compliance of the ZUN achieved by students with the standard established by the state is checked, and the assessment expresses the reaction to the degree and quality of this compliance, i.e. Ultimately, the monitoring and evaluation system for the teacher becomes a tool for notifying the public and the state about the state and problems of education in a given society and at this stage of its development, this provides grounds for predicting the directions for the development of education in the near and long term, making the necessary adjustments to the education system of the younger generations of providing the necessary assistance to both the student and the teacher.

The educational function determines the result of comparing the expected effect of learning with the actual result of learning the educational material by students: the completeness and awareness of knowledge, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in non-standard situations, the ability to choose the most appropriate means to complete the educational task: the dynamics of progress is established, the formation (unformation) of personality traits, necessary both for university life and outside it, the degree of development of basic mental operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization); it becomes possible to identify problem areas

in the work, to fix successful methods and techniques to analyze what training content it is advisable to expand and which to exclude from the curriculum.

On the part of the student, it is established what are the specific results of his educational activity; what is learned firmly, consciously, and what needs to be repeated, deepened, which aspects of educational activity have been formed and which need to be formed.

The educational function is expressed in the consideration of the formation of positive motives for learning and readiness for self-control as a factor in overcoming students' low self-esteem and anxiety.

Properly organized control and evaluation remove the students' fear of tests, reduce the level of anxiety, form the correct target settings, focus on independence and self-control.

The emotional function is manifested in the fact that any kind of assessment (including marks) creates a certain emotional reaction of the student. Indeed, assessment can inspire, direct to overcome difficulties, provide support, but it can also upset, put one in the category of "lagging behind", aggravate low self-esteem, disrupt contact with adults and peers.

The implementation of this most important function when checking learning outcomes is that the emotional reaction of the teacher must correspond to the emotional reaction of the student (please with him, grieve with him) and orient him towards success, express confidence that these results can be changed to the best. This provision correlates with one of the main laws of the pedagogy of high education - the student must learn from success. The situation of success and emotional well-being are the prerequisites for the student to calmly

accept the teacher's assessment, analyze the mistakes with him and outline ways to eliminate them.

The information function is the basis for the diagnosis of planning and forecasting. Its main feature is the ability to analyze the causes of unsuccessful results and outline specific ways to improve the educational process both from the side of the leader of this process and from the side of the follower.

The management function is very important for the student's self-control, his ability to analyze and correctly evaluate his activities, and adequately accept the teacher's assessment. The management function helps the teacher to identify gaps and shortcomings in the organization of the pedagogical process, mistakes in their activities ("what am I doing wrong...", "what needs to be done to...") and to correct the educational process. Thus, feedback is

established between the teacher and the student.

In conclusion, the ability to correctly apply "assessment pedagogy" is an important pedagogical art. It consists not only in the objectivity of the assessment. Comprehensive consideration of the psychological effect of assessment, the ability to use this effect in order to influence the student desired by the teacher, taking into account his individuality, is another, no less important aspect of this art. In order to make the right decision when setting a mark, you need to think in advance about a number of points that should be taken into account. Evaluation should be objective, but its objectivity should follow from the unity and interdependence of the pedagogical, psychological and sociological functions. In order for assessment to be most effective and contribute to the success of students, the teacher must act in a differentiated way.

References:

1. Bogdanov G.A.: "At the lessons of the Russian language", Moscow "Enlightenment", 2019
2. Bolotika L.R.: "Pedagogy", Moscow "Enlightenment", 2017
3. Vek Kh.: "Ratings and Marks", Moscow "Enlightenment", 2020
4. Vorontsov A.B.: "Some approaches to the issue of monitoring and evaluating the educational activities of students", journal "Teacher", No. 7, 2021
5. Yakovlev N.M.: "Methodology and technique of a lesson at university", Moscow "Enlightenment", 2015